

www.bjisrd.com

Surgical Treatment of Congenital Myopia

Khamrakulov Sobir Batirovich,

Assistant at the Department of Ophthalmology, Samarkand State Medical University
sobirjon-2101@mail.ru

***Abstract:** Myopia is a refractive error that is accompanied by a decrease in the quality of vision "from a distance." When diagnosed with myopia, or nearsightedness, a person sees objects located near the well, but has difficulty seeing objects that are far away.*

In the absence of proper treatment and the cause of the disease persists, myopia develops and vision steadily deteriorates. In the early stages of the disease, the decrease in visual acuity is compensated by accommodation, but the refractive system gradually loses its ability to compensate and complications of myopia develop. Ultimately, untreated myopia can lead to complete blindness.

Myopia can be a consequence of anatomical defects of the eyeball (incorrect size, shape). Myopia also develops due to defects in the refraction of light rays and even as a result of insufficient eye hygiene. In some cases, myopia occurs due to injuries, traumas and contusions of the eyeball.

***Key words:** myopia, pathogenesis, lenticular, pseudomyopia, stages.*

Input: Axial or axial. It is caused by excessive length of the anteroposterior axis of the eyeball and is not accompanied by refractive errors of light rays.

Lenticular. Develops against the background of an increase in the refractive power of light rays by the lens of the eye due to systemic diseases (for example, diabetes) or the use of certain medications.

With corneal damage. The cause of the disease is excessive curvature of the cornea, which is accompanied by an increase in the refractive power of this part of the optical system of the eye.

From the point of view of the mechanism of the disease, a distinction is made between true and false myopia. In the first case, there are pathological changes that are organic in nature and affect the surface of the eyeball, cornea, or lens itself. True myopia can be congenital (hereditary) or acquired. In the absence of appropriate treatment, the disease progresses and is accompanied by serious complications.

False myopia is a type of myopia that occurs in children or young people due to overexertion of the accommodative apparatus. When looking at close objects, the ciliary muscle contracts and increases the refractive power of the lens of the eye. If the ciliary muscle remains in a state of contraction for a long time, metabolic processes and neuroregulation in the optical system are disrupted. When trying to examine distant objects, in a state of spasm of the ciliary muscle, the refractive power of the lens does not change, the image appears unclear and blurry. This condition is called accommodation spasm and false myopia.

With pseudomyopia, there is no damage to the eyeball or optical system, and this condition is temporary and goes away on its own after the causative factor is eliminated. The list of causes that provoke pseudomyopia includes eye strain, poor sleep and nutrition, and physical overwork.

Myopia in children can be congenital or physiological. Congenital occurs mainly in premature babies, born less than 37 weeks after development in the womb. The baby is born with an elongated eyeball. As a result, the rays are focused in front of the retina, and the newborn is diagnosed with myopia. Congenital myopia usually disappears on its own within a few months after the baby is born, as the size and anatomy of the eyeball change, as a result of which the refractive power is naturally corrected.

Research methods and materials: Physiological myopia develops in children aged 5-10 years during the period of intensive growth and development of the eyeball. At this stage, with an excessive increase in the anteroposterior size of the organ, the focusing of light rays is disturbed - they converge in front of the retina, as a result of which the ability to see objects at a distance is impaired. As a person ages, physiological myopia can become more pronounced until the age of 18, and the formation of the eyeball stops. In some cases, the disease persists up to 25 years.

The development of myopia in the early stages is accompanied by a gradual deterioration of vision and the patient's loss of the ability to clearly distinguish objects located far from him. In conditions of slow development of the disease, this symptom may not be pronounced enough, and patients associate the deterioration of vision with overwork. As myopia progresses, the quality of images of distant objects deteriorates significantly. At the same time, working with objects located nearby is not accompanied by discomfort or difficulties.

The development of myopia can be indicated by the patient's desire to squint when trying to see distant objects. This symptom occurs due to a partial narrowing of the pupil, which causes a certain part of the pupil to be blocked and changes the nature of the light rays passing through the lens of the eye. Due to this, the quality of vision improves. In addition, partial closure of the eyelids leads to a flattening of the cornea of the eye, which improves the clarity of objects in the case of a combination of myopia and corneal astigmatism.

Results: Also, as the disease progresses, the patient develops additional symptoms resulting from damage to the refractive system and deterioration of visual acuity. The list of such symptoms includes:

Headache. Headache attacks are accompanied by constant tension of the accommodation apparatus and impaired blood circulation and nutrition at the level of the ciliary muscle and other structures. In addition, the occurrence of headaches is influenced by the difficulty in seeing distant objects, as a result of which the nervous system is overstrained.

Painful eyes. A burning sensation and pain may occur after the patient begins to work with objects at close range (for example, reading or working on a computer). These symptoms are also caused by overexertion of the optical system and accommodation defects. The burning sensation is directly caused by accommodation spasm.

Lacrimation. This symptom often appears in myopia during prolonged examination of objects at close range and is found even in completely healthy people. If there is no disease, the symptom disappears after a short rest. Similarly, with myopia, increased lacrimation is a reaction to bright sunlight or strong artificial lighting. The reason for its occurrence is a pronounced expansion of the pupil against the background of damage to the ciliary muscle. Excessive light enters the eye, and the secretion of tear fluid is aimed at protecting the eye.

In addition, with myopia, the size of the pupil may change towards widening. This symptom becomes more pronounced as the disease progresses and is caused by an increase in the size of the eyeball.

Diagnosis of the disease is carried out by qualified ophthalmologists. The basis for suspecting myopia may be the patient's characteristic complaints, but a definite diagnosis is possible only after a complete examination. In order to prescribe treatment appropriate to the patient's condition, it is necessary to determine the type, form and stage of the disease.

True myopia cannot go away without outside help and, without proper treatment, remains with the patient for life. At the same time, a timely visit to the doctor allows not only to stop the progression of the disease, but also to restore vision. Modern methods of eliminating myopia allow you to restore adequate quality of vision even in advanced, advanced stages of the disease. Treatment should be started as soon as possible, before the development of irreversible complications and pathological changes in the retina or other structures of the eye.

Myopia is corrected by the following methods:

1. glasses and lenses,
2. laser correction methods,
3. eye lens replacement,
4. surgical operations.
5. Vitamin therapy, medications, and physical therapy are also used.

The simplest way to correct myopia is with glasses with a diverging lens. This method helps restore normal distance vision and prevents the possibility of developing pathological processes that cause complications of myopia.

To correct any degree of myopia, the patient is prescribed contact lenses. Unlike ordinary glasses, they fit tightly to the surface of the cornea and form a single system of refraction of light rays. Thus, a more accurate correction effect is achieved.

Patients with anisometropia are recommended to wear lenses, which is an eye pathology accompanied by different refractive powers on the left and right sides. In cases of weak anisometropia, the indicators of which are less than 3 diopters, simple glasses with different lenses can be used for correction, but in the middle and advanced stages of the disease, lenses are mainly prescribed.

Regardless of the diagnosis and the patient's condition, neither lenses nor glasses cure the disease, but only correct vision. However, the use of optical devices helps to prevent complications.

Discussion: Laser treatment of myopia is in many cases the most effective and modern method of restoring visual acuity and preventing further pathological changes. The laser treatment method is based on correcting the curvature of the central part of the cornea using laser beams in the direction of its contraction. Thus, the refractive power of the cornea is weakened, as a result of which normal

visual acuity is restored. Laser correction is prescribed to patients with a refractive error of 1 to 15 diopters, the choice of method depends on the thickness of the cornea.

In preparation for laser surgery, the patient must undergo a comprehensive examination using computer diagnostic methods and mandatory ophthalmological examination procedures. During the examination, information is collected about the condition of the cornea, the lens of the eye and the eyeball. This data is entered into a computer program and used to calculate the optimal correction parameters. The laser treatment process itself is carried out under the full control of the computer program, due to which the risk of error due to the human factor is excluded.

The procedure lasts an average of 10-15 minutes (taking into account the impact on both eyes). Before this, the patient enters the operating room and changes into sterile clothing. Then he is placed on the operating table, and the doctor adjusts the laser device depending on the patient's condition and the area of intervention. To eliminate pain and discomfort during the operation, the patient is given anesthetic eye drops that block the sensitivity receptors. In addition, local instillation anesthesia prevents involuntary blinking and other reactions of the patient to the doctor's manipulations.

After the anesthetic drops have taken effect, the patient's head is fixed in a strictly vertical position. Additional eyelid restraints are placed to prevent blinking. This is completely painless and may be accompanied by only minor discomfort. After checking the patient's head position, the laser device is aligned over the operated eye and the patient is asked to look at the flashing light indicator.

During the correction, a superficial shallow incision is made. The cut part of the cornea is lifted and used as a surgical flap. Next, a laser beam is applied to the eye, which, according to the parameters set by the computer, vaporizes the excess curvature of the cornea to change its shape. The laser acts on each eye of the patient for no more than 1-1.5 minutes. After this stage of laser correction is completed, the corneal flap is returned to its original position. There is no need to put stitches - the incision site is sealed by itself, for this the flap fits snugly against the cornea, and the patient remains motionless for several more minutes.

After completing the treatment, the doctor will conduct a follow-up examination of the patient and a post-operative vision test. This stage lasts an average of 1-2 hours. The patient returns home within a few hours after the operation. It is necessary to strictly follow the doctor's recommendations for recovery for the next 1-2 weeks.

In conditions of high myopia, up to 20 diopters, the patient is prescribed a lens replacement operation with the installation of an intraocular lens.

The surgical opening in the eyes closes on its own without stitches. The doctor will conduct a follow-up examination and give the patient appropriate recommendations on behavior and lifestyle rules for several days after the operation. The recovery process is monitored by the ophthalmologist during scheduled appointments;

Surgical treatment of myopia is prescribed in cases of high myopia, which is prone to rapid progression, with a deterioration of vision by 1 or more diopters per year. An indication for surgery is also the lack of positive results from conservative treatment methods and the use of physiotherapy.

Typically, the surgeon's task is to strengthen the back wall of the eyeball using scleroplasty. This helps prevent the development of concomitant complications associated with stretching of the eyeball and damage to the retina and blood vessels. Special scleroplastic fabrics are used to strengthen the sclera. The introduction of these devices behind the back of the sclera is carried out using a special curved needle and a small incision.

Scleroplasty is a simple surgical procedure that has no strict contraindications and is performed on an outpatient basis. In general, treatment with this method does not last more than a day, after which the patient can return home. Restrictions for the postoperative period include avoiding eye strain and provoking factors.

Conclusion: Myopia itself is not cured by this surgical method, but the progression of the disease is slowed down or completely stopped. Under these conditions, further progression of myopia is stopped in 95% of adult patients and 70% of children. Scleroplasty can be combined with alternative methods of myopia therapy - glasses or lenses, laser correction, etc.

Myopia of any degree requires treatment, since the progression of the disease changes the shape of the eyeball and disrupts the blood supply to the internal structures, thereby causing complications. In most cases, with a high degree of myopia, serious complications develop. Their list includes pathologies of varying complexity - from amblyopia to cataracts and retinal detachment. The main danger with advanced myopia is the development of irreversible blindness.

List of used literature:

1. Avetisov E.S. Miyopi. M.: Tibbiyot, 1999. P. 59. [Avetisov ES Miyopi. M.: Tibbiyot, 1999. S. 59 (rus tilida)].
2. Akopyan A.I. va boshqalar glaukoma va miyopidagi optik asab diskining xususiyatlari. // Glaukoma. 2005. No 4. B. 57–62. [Akopyan AI Glaukoma va miyopidagi optik diskning xususiyatlari // Glaukoma. 2005. No 4. P. 57–62 (rus tilida)].
3. Dal N.Yu. Makula karotinoidlari. Ular bizni yoshga bog'liq makula naslidan himoya qila oladimi? // Oftalmologiya gazetasi. 2008. No 3. B. 51–53. [Dal NY Makula karotenoidlari. Ular bizni yoshga bog'liq makula naslidan himoya qila oladimi? // Oftalmologik jurnallar. 2008. No 3. P. 51–53 (rus tilida)].
4. Eroshevskiy T.I., Bochkareva A.A. Ko'z kasalliklari. M.: Tibbiyot, 1989. P. 414. [Eroshevskiy TI, Bochkareva AA Ko'z kasalliklari. M.: Tibbiyot, 1980. S. 414 (rus tilida)].
5. Zykova A.V., Rzayev V.M., Eskina E.N. Turli yoshdagi normal bemorlarda makula pigmentining optik zichligini o'rganish: VI rus tilidagi ishlar. umummilliy oftalmol. forum. Ilmiy maqolalar to'plami. M., 2013. 2-jild. S. 685–688. [Zykova AV, Rzaev VM, Eskina EN. Turli yoshdagi bemorlarda normal makula pigment optik zichligini o'rganish // VI Rossiya milliy oftalmologiya forumi. Ilmiy ishlar to'plami. Moskva, 2013. jild. 2. B. 685–688 (rus tilida)].
6. Kuznetsova M.V. Miyopiyaning sabablari va uni davolash. M.: MEDpress-inform, 2005. P. 176. [Kuznetsova MV Miyopi rivojlanishining asosiy sabablari va uni davolash. M: Medpress-inform, 2005. S. 176 (rus tilida)].
7. Libman EC, Shaxova EB Rossiyada ko'rish organining patologiyasi tufayli ko'rlik va nogironlik // Oftalmologiya byulleteni. 2006. No 1. B. 35–37. [Libman ES, Shaxova, EV Rossiyada ko'z patologiyasi tufayli ko'rlik va nogironlik // Vestnik oftalmologii. 2006. No 1. P. 35–37 (rus tilida)].
8. Oftalmologiya. Milliy qo'llanma / ed. S.E. Avetisova, E.A. Egorova, L.K. Moshetova, V.V. Neroeva, H.P. Taxchidi. M.: GEOTAR-Media, 2008. P. 944. [Shifokorlar S. E. Avetisov, E. A. Egorov, L. K. Moshetova, V. V. Neroev, H. P. Taxchidi uchun glaukoma bo'yicha milliy ko'rsatmalar. M.: GEOTAR-Media, 2008. S. 944 (rus tilida)].

9. Remesnikov I.A. Nisbatan ko'z qorachig'i blokirovkasi bilan birlamchi yopiq burchakli glaukomada normada va ko'zning anatomik tuzilmalarining sagittal o'lchamlari o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik naqshlari: Dissertatsiya referati. diss. ... nomzod asal. fanlar. Volgograd, 2007. P. 2. [Remesnikov IA. Anatomik tuzilmalarning sagittal o'lchamlari normada va birlamchi burchakni yopuvchi glaukomada nisbatan o'quvchi blokirovkasi bilan aloqasi: Dissertatsiya. Volgograd, 2007. S. 2 (rus tilida)].
10. Slovko E.L. Miyopi. Refraktiv xato - bu kasallik // Astraxan ekologik ta'lim byulleteni. 2014 yil. No 2 (28). B. 160–165. [Sluvko EL miyopi. Refraktsiyaning buzilishi kasallikdir // Astraxanskiy Vestnik Ekologicheskogo obrazovaniya. 2014 yil. No 2 (28). S. 160–165 (rus tilida)].
11. Eskina E.N., Zykova A.V. Miyopi bo'lgan bemorlarda glaukoma rivojlanish xavfining dastlabki mezonlari // Oftalmologiya. 2014. 11-jild. No 2. 59–63-betlar. [Eskina EN, Zykova AV Miyopi bo'lgan bemorlarda glaukoma rivojlanish xavfining dastlabki mezonlari // Oftalmologiya. 2014. 11-jild. No 2. S. 59–63 (rus tilida)].
12. Abell RG, Hewitt AW, Andric M., Allen PL, Verma N. Sog'lom Avstraliya populyatsiyasida makula pigmentining optik zichligini aniqlash uchun heteroxromatik miltillovchi fotometriyadan foydalanish // Graefes Arch Clin Exp Ophthalmol. 2014. jild. 252 (3). B. 417–421.
13. Beatty S., Koh HH, Phil M., Henson D., Boulton M. Yoshga bog'liq makula nasli patogenezida oksidlovchi stressning roli // Surv. Ophthalmol. 2000. jild. 45. 115–134-betlar.
14. Suyak RA, Henle tolasi membranalarida Landrum JT Makula pigmenti Haidinger cho'tkalari uchun model // Vision Res. 1984. jild. 24. 103–108-betlar.
15. Bressler NM, Bressler SB, Childs AL Yoshga bog'liq makula naslining gemorragik koroidal neovaskulyar lezyonlari uchun jar